

3-Hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one as an Analytical Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(v)

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3-Hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) forms a dark yellow 1 : 2 (V : HTC) complex with V^V species in 0.04–0.30 M CH₃COOH medium, which is extracted in benzene and has λ_{\max} at 415–425 nm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and standard deviation are $3.27 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.0016 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$ and ± 0.0015 , respectively at 420 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 0–1.3 $\mu\text{g V ml}^{-1}$ solvent phase. The method has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of vanadium in a wide variety of synthetic and technical samples.

Chromone derivatives constitute a versatile class of analytical reagents for transition elements. Some of the reagents^{1–3} reported for the determination of vanadium are sensitive^{1,2} but require 8–16 min waiting time for full colour development. Almost all these methods suffer from large number of interferences and thus have limited applications. In continuation of our work on the use of such compounds⁴ as extractants for molybdenum and niobium, the present communication describes a simple and rapid spectrophotometric method of determination of V^V using 3-hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) as a highly selective reagent.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(v) formed a stable dark yellow complex with HTC in CH₃COOH medium at room temperature which was quantitatively extracted in benzene with a single contact. In mineral acids fading of the colour was observed. For achieving optimum and constant absorbance, 0.04–0.30 M CH₃COOH and 0.9–1.5 ml of 0.05% HTC solution containing $\leq 13 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$ in 10 ml final volume were found sufficient when shaken with equal volume of benzene for 5–75 s.

The absorption spectrum of V^V-HTC complex in benzene showed λ_{\max} at 415–425 nm, where the reagent blank absorbed negligibly. The complex obeyed Beer's law upto $1.3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of V with a molar absorptivity of $3.27 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The optimum concentration range to determine vanadium accurately, as obtained from Ringbom plot at 420 nm, was 0.28–1.23 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity was $0.0016 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$. Ten replicate determinations containing $1 \mu\text{g V ml}^{-1}$ gave mean absorbance value of 0.639 with a standard deviation of ± 0.0015 . The composition of the complex as determined by Job's method of continuous variations was found to be 1 : 2, which was further confirmed by mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of diverse ions on the determination of $10 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}/10 \text{ ml}$ aqueous phase was examined and the tolerance limit (mg) of various ions (shown in parentheses) were as follows : bromide, sulphate, nitrate, thiourea (100 each); chloride (80), iodide, phosphate (70

each); thiocyanate (50); acetate (15); tartrate (10); fluoride (5); citrate (1); hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5); glycerol (0.1 ml); Co^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Mn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sr^{II} (10 each); Cd^{II} (9); Be^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} (7 each); Th^{IV}, Ni^{II} (5 each); Cu^{II} (4); U^{VI}, As^V (1 each); Ti^{IV}, Nb^V (0.7 each); Cr^{VI}, Se^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Sb^{III}, Al^{III} (0.5 each); Re^{VII}, Ta^V (0.1 each); Os^{VIII}, Pt^{IV}, Sn^{II} (0.07 each); Ag^I (0.06); Ir^{III} (0.05); Pd^{II} (0.03); W^{VI}, Au^{III} (0.02 each) and Ru^{III} (0.01). Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI} and Fe^{III} caused <1 % error in presence of respective masking agents as described under Experimental. Upto 20 mg of Fe^{III} was tolerable when it was separated as its hydroxide from the sample solution using NaOH prior to vanadium extraction. Oxalate, H₂O₂, EDTA and ascorbic acid even in traces interfered seriously.

Applications : Several synthetic mixtures (some of them analogous to palau and nichroloy), steel alloy and flue dust samples were analysed by the proposed procedure. The results obtained were quite satisfactory (Table 1). The method was accurate, rapid, sensitive and selective and compared favourably with the existing ones (Table 2).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF V^V IN SYNTHETIC AND REAL SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Composition of sample (mg)	V added μg	V found* μg
1.	Ni(0.06), Pt(0.02), Pd(0.02) ^a	10.0	10.1
2.	Fe(0.25), Ni(0.12), Cr(0.1), Mn(0.005) ^a	5.0	5.0
3.	Cu(2.0), Zn(5.0), Mn(5.0)	5.0	5.2
4.	Ti(0.5), Ta(0.01), Zr(0.01) ^b	7.0	7.1
5.	W(0.01), U(0.5), Cr(0.1)	12.0	12.0
6.	Ni(2.0), Cu(2.0), Co(5.0)	10.0	10.0
7.	Ba(5.0), Ce(0.1), Se(0.1)	5.0	5.0
8.	High speed steel super rapid extra 500 ^c (200)	1% ^d	0.951%
9.	Reverberatory flue dust (100)	5.0	4.82

*Average of duplicate analyses.

^aCompositions analogous to palau and nichroloy respectively. ^bIn presence of 2.5 mg sodium fluoride. ^cIn presence of 70 mg sodium phosphate. ^dCertified value.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE PRESENT METHOD WITH OTHER METHODS

Sl no	Aqueous condition	Solvent, λ_{\max} nm	Sandell's sensitivity, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Interfering metal ions
1.	V^V , pH 2.8–4.8, 3-Hydroxyflavone ^a	Chloroform, 480	0.009, 5.5×10^3	Fe^{III} , W^{VI}
2.	V^V , pH 1.9–2.8, Benzoylphenyl-hydroxylamine	–, 525	0.01, 5.094×10^3	Mo^{VI} , Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV}
3.	V^V , pH 3.5–4.5, Picolinealdehyde benzothiazolylhydrazone ^c	–, 528	0.0033, 1.54×10^4	$Fe^{II,III}$, Co^{II} , Pd^{II}
4.	V^V , pH 6–8, Dithionite, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline ^d	Chloroform, 420	0.006, 7.27×10^3	Mo^{VI}
5.	V^V , $HClO_4$, persulphate, acetone, ammonium acetate, pH 3–3.5, waiting time 5 min, 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) ^e	Chloroform, 615	0.003, 1.69×10^4	Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Co^{II} , Bi^{III} , U^{VI}
6.	V^V , pH 5.25–6.2, waiting time 1 h, 4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol (PAR) ^e	–, 545	0.001, 3.6×10^4	Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ta^V , Zn^{II} , Ag^I , Cr^{VI} , Bi^{III}
7.	Present method	Benzene, 415–425	0.0016, 3.27×10^4	$Mo^{VI} > 0.5 \mu\text{g}$ and $Zr^{IV} > 2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 7. ^eRef. 8.

Experimental

A Shimadzu-140-02 spectrophotometer was used. A stock solution of vanadium (1 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving sodium metavanadate (sd fine, A.R.) in deionized water and standardized by iron(II) sulphate method volumetrically⁹; aliquots were suitably diluted to give $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ solution. The solutions of other metal ions were prepared by dissolving their analytical grade salts in water or dilute acids to give $\leq 10 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$ concentrations of the ions. 3-Hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) was synthesized by the literature method¹⁰, and dissolved in ethanol to give a 0.05% (w/v) solution. Acetic acid solution (2 M) was prepared by suitable dilution of glacial acetic acid. Benzene (Qualigens SQ) was distilled and the b.p. 79.5–80° fraction was used.

High speed steel super rapid extra 500 sample (0.2 g) was dissolved by boiling with aqua regia⁹, the dried mass dissolved in deionized water and the volume made to 100

ml. The metal content was determined in an aliquot (1 ml) of this solution by the proposed method after adding 70 mg phosphate before adding HTC.

Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) obtained from copper manufacturing unit, was mixed with a solution of known vanadium content (1 mg). It was dried, fused with Na_2O_2 , dissolved in water, neutralized with CH_3COOH and the volume made to 100 ml. To 0.5 ml of this solution was added 70 mg of phosphate, and vanadium determined by the proposed method.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the test solution (containing upto $13 \mu\text{g } V^V$) were added 2 M CH_3COOH (1 ml) and 0.05% HTC (1.2 ml) and its volume was made upto 10 ml with deionized water. It was then equilibrated with benzene (10 ml) for 1 min. The organic extract was passed through Whatman No.41 filter paper (pretreated with benzene) to remove water droplets and its absorbance measured at 420 nm against the reagent blank.

For samples containing 0.5 mg of Fe^{III} , 20 μg of Zr^{IV} and 5 μg of Mo^{VI} , 70 mg of phosphate, 2.5 and 5 mg of fluoride were added respectively as their sodium salts to mask these ions.

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